

THE END OF THE KHIVA KHANATE AND THE ACTIVITIES OF JUNAYD KHAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748745>

Abstract

This article analyzes the struggle of Turkmen leader Junayd Khan against the Soviet government and the political processes in the Khiva Khanate from 1918 to 1920, as well as the eventual end of the Khiva Khanate.

Keywords: Junayd Khan, Turkmens, Khiva Khanate, Soviet government, revolution, Young Khivans movement

Introduction

After the Russian troops withdrew from the Khiva Khanate in 1918, Junayd Khan, who had military forces, established his rule in the Khanate. He had returned from Iran in the autumn of 1917, taking advantage of the situation. Asfandiyar Khan, who did not have his own army, had previously relied on Russian forces to maintain his rule. After the Russians left, he lost his main support and fell under Junayd Khan's influence. Junayd Khan established his rule in Khiva and appointed his loyalists to the positions of local rulers. However, his men lacked experience in governance.

Taking advantage of the situation, Asfandiyar Khan, with the help of the Turkmens, began to dissolve the Majlis and eliminate the core of the Young Khivans who had formed it. He first bribed the leader of the Turkmen Ushoq tribe, Said Muhammadbek, to kill Rahmonbergan Yakub o'g'li and Kurbonboy Qalantar. In April 1917, the punishment of the young Bukharians in the Emirate of Bukhara led Asfandiyar Khan to intensify his actions against the Young Khivans. Asfandiyar Khan offered gifts to Junayd Khan's son, Eshshi, and had the Young Khivans who had held important government posts killed, including Prime Minister Husseinbek Matmurodov, his successor Isokhujani, Foreign Minister Abdusalomkhujani (son of Said Isломkhujani), and Treasurer Tolibkhujani.

The properties of the Young Khivans were confiscated, and their families were expelled. Those who had connections with them were also punished. On the same day, Junayd Khan's forces executed 24 people who had participated in an April 1917 demonstration. However, later, Asfandiyar Khan himself was assassinated by Junayd Khan. According to P. Yusupov, Asfandiyar Khan, in

order to avenge the death of the Young Khivans, sent Junayd Khan false information about requesting help from the Bolsheviks. As a result, Junayd Khan sent his troops, led by his son Eshshi, on October 1, 1918, to kill Asfandiyar Khan.

Junayd Khan appointed the more obedient Said Abdullo to the throne. Asfandiyar Khan's brother, Said Abdullo, was a weak-willed man who was not interested in state affairs. To manage state affairs, Junayd Khan appointed his own man, Davlat Murod Makhram.

After establishing his full rule over the Khiva Khanate, Junayd Khan began to make efforts to reclaim the territories on the right bank of the Amu Darya that were under the control of the Bolsheviks. On November 24, 1918, he launched an attack on the city of Turtkul (formerly known as Petro-Alexandrovsk) with an army of ten thousand. The Bolsheviks had a garrison of eight hundred men in Turtkul. When Junayd Khan's forces encountered strong resistance, they laid siege to the city. His forces also attacked Nukus and laid siege there as well. For support, the Bolsheviks sent 180 men from the "Tashkent" and "Verney" ships from Chardzhou. On the tenth day of the siege, a counterattack by the Bolsheviks resulted in a large loss for Junayd Khan's forces, and they were defeated. Despite having a large army, Junayd Khan's forces were disorganized. After this defeat, Junayd Khan temporarily halted his military actions against the Bolsheviks.

By 1919, Junayd Khan and his officials' acts of violence and arbitrariness towards the population, the removal of gold and silver currency from circulation, the introduction of paper and cotton money, the forced confiscation of horses and other livestock, attacks on rebellious villages and settlements, the conscription of people and transport vehicles for the war effort, the breakdown of irrigation systems, and the disruption of former trade connections had caused the economy and daily life of the Khanate to fall into disarray.

By the beginning of 1919, the political situation in the Khiva Khanate was also tense. Junayd Khan's attack on Turtkul had failed, and despite retreating, the state of war persisted. However, by this time, both Junayd Khan and the Bolsheviks were in a difficult position, and neither side was able to continue active military operations. Junayd Khan's popularity had fallen among the people, and his army's Turkmen units, which had participated in the unsuccessful attack on Turtkul, had returned to their homeland. Not only the Uzbek population but also several Turkmen tribes were dissatisfied with Junayd Khan's rule. This discontent gradually turned into an open armed resistance against him.

The situation was also difficult for the Bolsheviks, as Ataman Dutov's White Guard forces had captured Orenburg, thus separating Turkestan from Russia. Furthermore, uprisings by the Ural Cossacks and the Karakalpaks had broken out against the Bolshevik government in the Amu Darya region.

In this challenging situation, both sides sought a path to reconciliation. In 1919, the Bolshevik government in Turkestan sent an extraordinary mission headed by A.F. Christoforov, a member of the Turkestan Revolutionary Committee, to negotiate with Junayd Khan. Junayd Khan accepted the proposal for talks and invited the mission to his residence in the Takhta-Kala fortress. After two days of negotiations, a peace agreement was signed on April 9. According to the agreement, both sides pledged to halt military actions. The Soviet government recognized the right of the Khiva population to determine their own destiny. Both sides agreed to exchange representatives and allow Khiva to open a diplomatic mission in Tashkent and Moscow, while the Soviet government could establish a mission in Khiva. Both sides also pledged to ensure free movement and security for trade routes passing through their territories, both land and water. In exchange for participation in military operations against the Soviet forces, amnesty was declared for Turkmens who were Russian citizens, and they were granted the right to freely choose their place of residence.

In June 1919, Junayd Khan declared a general military mobilization in the Khiva Khanate. Armed groups were quickly formed, and the mobilized people had to buy their own weapons and ammunition. Special military taxes, called "war tax," were imposed on every household that did not provide manpower for military service, collecting 300 soms from each. Junayd Khan sought external assistance to strengthen his armed forces, first establishing contacts with Filichev and Khan Maksim, who were operating against the Soviet government in the Amu Darya region, and agreed to act together. He also sought to form a military alliance with the Emir of Bukhara. The Emir of Bukhara sent eleven Austrian military prisoners to Khiva to repair weapons.

In October 1919, Admiral Kolchak's forces, consisting of 130 Cossacks and 8 officers, along with a large number of weapons and ammunition, sent support to Junayd Khan. By the end of 1919, Junayd Khan managed to raise his army to 17,000 cavalymen. However, after the peace agreement, taking advantage of the temporary calm, the Bolshevik government also began preparing to invade the Khiva Khanate.

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By the autumn of 1919, Junayd Khan's armed groups' lawlessness, violence, and destruction caused the people's dissatisfaction with his rule to grow, and the situation became even more tense. The Bolsheviks took advantage of this and intensified their activities in the Khiva Khanate. By this time, the Bolsheviks had a favorable opportunity to invade the Khiva Khanate, as the Red Army had defeated Kolchak's forces and achieved significant success on the Caspian Front.

In November 1919, one of the Turkmen leaders, Qoshmamad Khan, in the Old Urgench district, revolted against Junayd Khan and established contact with the Young Khivans. Using the pretext of this rebellion, Soviet forces invaded the Khiva Khanate. In February 1920, the Soviet southern group of troops entered the Khiva capital without facing serious resistance. In the areas captured by the Soviet forces, the violence and looting carried out by the Bolshevik soldiers surpassed that of the Tsarist imperial army. Red Army soldiers conducted their looting under the leadership of their commanders.

On April 6, 1920, the chairman of the Turkfront Revolutionary Tribunal, I.R. Fonstein, sent a telegram to Tashkent, describing the atrocities committed by the Red Army in Khiva. He wrote: "We have never seen such horrors anywhere. This was organized military looting. Women and girls were taken away, kept as captives or slaves, sold in markets in Petro-Alexandrovsk and Khiva, the palaces of Khiva were looted, and Red Army soldiers shot anyone they encountered in order to seize their property." No measures were taken against the perpetrators of these crimes; on the contrary, they were later promoted to higher positions and rewarded.

On February 2, 1920, under pressure from the Bolsheviks, Said Abdullakhon signed a manifesto renouncing the throne. A new temporary coalition government was formed under the leadership of J. Sultanmurodov. Thus, the Khiva Khanate came to an end.

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